

EUC_SOH: A Vehicle Health and Usage Monitoring System to Enhance the Safety of Electric Unicycles

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[†]This author conceived the study, implemented the EUC SOH framework, performed the analyses and wrote the manuscript.

Abstract

Electric unicycles (EUCs) have evolved into high-performance personal vehicles capable of daily commuting at substantial speeds and energies, yet they remain largely outside the scope of established vehicle health and usage monitoring practices. Sudden loss of propulsion, often suspected to be linked to electrical or thermal limitations, can lead to severe rider injuries, while existing mobile applications focus mainly on real-time dashboards and trip logging without providing long-term, vehicle-level health assessment.

This paper introduces EUC_SOH, a vehicle health and usage monitoring system for electric unicycles that operates on ride logs collected over several thousands to tens of thousands of kilometers. EUC_SOH derives empirical, physically interpretable indicators from pack-level telemetry and usage data, including equivalent pack resistance, battery-dominated resistance normalized to 25°C, power MOSFET resistance at operating temperature, voltage sag metrics, and current and temperature-based stress indicators. An optional stylized ageing simulator and dedicated anomaly and degradation detection modules, including CUSUM-like change detection, are used to characterize both slow degradation trends and rare out-of-family events at the vehicle level under realistic data constraints.

We evaluate EUC_SOH on real-world datasets from multiple EUCs, complemented by simulated ageing and fault scenarios. Results on long-term field data show that the system can consistently track, on the wheels studied, gradual increases in equivalent and battery-dominated resistance, identify sustained changes in sag and temperature behaviour, and detect the first occurrence of major deviations after tens of thousands of kilometers, even when global statistics remain apparently normal on the datasets studied. We discuss how such vehicle-level health indicators, built from end-user-accessible logs, could support

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047 safer operation, early maintenance decisions and more systematic consideration
048 of electric unicycles as serious vehicles within the broader framework of health
049 and usage monitoring systems.

050 **Keywords:** Electric unicycles, Micromobility safety, Health and usage monitoring
051 systems, Battery state of health, Power electronics degradation, Condition-based
052 maintenance

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056 1 Introduction

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058 Personal electric vehicles such as electric unicycles (EUCs) have rapidly evolved from
059 niche gadgets to high-performance transportation devices capable of sustaining daily
060 commuting and interurban trips at substantial speeds and energies. Yet, EUCs largely
061 remain outside the scope of traditional vehicle safety engineering and health and
062 usage monitoring practices, even though a single loss of propulsion typically results in
063 immediate loss of balance and a high risk of injury for the rider.

064 Existing national and international reports on micromobility safety mainly consider
065 aggregated categories such as e-scooters, e-bikes and other motorised micromobility
066 devices, and do not isolate electric unicycles as a separate class [1–3]. In France,
067 the annual road safety reports from ONISR document a marked increase in crashes,
068 serious injuries and fatalities among micromobility users since 2019, but without an
069 EUC-specific breakdown of causes or failure modes [1]. In the United States, the Con-
070 sumer Product Safety Commission reports similar trends for micromobility products
071 over the 2017–2023 period, again without distinguishing EUCs within this group [2].
072 At European level, ETSC analyses e-scooter safety and other micromobility devices
073 in aggregate, calling for improved data collection and mandatory safety standards,
074 but does not provide EUC-specific statistics [3]. To the best of our knowledge, there
075 is therefore no official dataset that systematically separates EUC incidents caused
076 by intrinsic hardware or powertrain failures from those caused by collisions or loss-
077 of-control. For EUCs, suspected sudden loss-of-power events are mostly reported
078 informally in online communities, typically without access to detailed vehicle logs or
079 structured post-mortem analysis.

080 Compared to other personal electric vehicles (PEVs) such as e-scooters or skate-
081 boards, electric unicycles have a much steeper learning curve: riding safely requires
082 active balance control in both pitch and roll, and beginners must overcome a non-trivial
083 entry barrier before reaching basic proficiency. Once this barrier is passed, however,
084 EUCs offer a unique combination of versatility and capability: large wheels, high torque
085 and, on recent models, long-travel suspension allow riders to negotiate curbs, potholes,
086 rough tracks and off-road sections without dismounting, while sustaining urban cruis-
087 ing speeds and long commutes on a single vehicle. In practice, a single EUC can cover
088 use cases that would otherwise require multiple PEVs (urban scooter, trekking bike,
089 light off-road vehicle) or even a car, which explains why experienced riders tend to push
090 these machines close to their electrical and thermal limits in real-world conditions.

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By contrast, in other transportation domains, Health and Usage Monitoring Systems (HUMS) and vehicle health monitoring systems are routinely used to collect on-board sensor data, derive health indicators and support condition-based maintenance for safety-critical vehicles, including military land platforms [4–7]. These systems rely on long-term usage data and diagnostic algorithms to detect degradation trends and rare anomalies, thereby reducing unexpected failures and improving availability. In parallel, a large body of work on lithium-ion batteries has shown that capacity fade and the increase of DC internal resistance are major contributors to state-of-health (SoH) reduction, and that resistance or sag under load provide robust health indicators when compared under comparable operating conditions [8–11]. Recent studies have further emphasized the importance of non-linear ageing trajectories with distinct “elbows” or regimes of accelerated degradation in internal resistance and related metrics, and their implications for failure risk and end-of-life decisions [12, 13]. For power MOSFETs and other power semiconductor devices, changes in on-state resistance, junction temperature and related electrical parameters have been widely investigated as precursors of degradation and failure in accelerated ageing, power-cycling and condition-monitoring studies [14–19]. However, to the best of our knowledge, no HUMS-like framework has been proposed and evaluated for electric unicycles considered as everyday vehicles, nor has the combined long-term evolution of battery and power electronics indicators been systematically studied at the vehicle level for this class of devices.

In this work, we introduce *EUC_SOH*, a vehicle-level health and usage monitoring system for electric unicycles. *EUC_SOH* operates on ride logs collected over several thousands to tens of thousands of kilometers, using signals available to end-users (pack-level telemetry, motor and controller temperatures, usage patterns) to monitor the health of the energy and power stages, including both the battery pack and the power MOSFET stage. The system combines interpretable feature extraction, an ageing simulator and anomaly/degradation detection mechanisms to identify subtle deviations and rare major events in long-term field data, at both slow-degradation and single-outlier scales. We show on real-world EUC datasets and simulated ageing scenarios that *EUC_SOH* can provide actionable health indicators that could support maintenance decisions and risk analysis for EUCs.

Although this work focuses on electric unicycles as a particularly demanding and under-studied class of personal electric vehicles, the overall approach is not EUC-specific. Any micromobility platform that exposes comparable pack-level telemetry (voltage, current, temperatures) and trip logs through its companion application or telematics backend could, in principle, host a similar vehicle-level health and usage monitoring layer. The main constraints are the availability and quality of the exposed signals, not the details of the vehicle architecture, which suggests that the concepts explored here may be transferable to other PEVs such as e-scooters and e-bikes as their logging capabilities mature.

139 2 Background and related work

140 2.1 Electric unicycles in the literature

141 Existing academic work on electric unicycles has largely focused on structural design
142 and control for self-balancing and trajectory tracking. Early and more recent con-
143 tributions treat the EUC as a challenging case for nonlinear control and mobile
144 robotics, addressing modelling, stabilisation and path-following controllers, often val-
145 idated on laboratory prototypes [20–23]. These studies demonstrate that EUCs are
146 technically viable and controllable, but they do not consider long-term field usage,
147 health monitoring of the energy and power stages, or safety implications of component
148 degradation.

149 A second line of work has explored prototype design and feasibility of electric uni-
150 cycles as alternative urban mobility options, sometimes emphasising potential benefits
151 in terms of congestion and local pollution [20]. However, these prototypes are not
152 evaluated as long-lived vehicles with monitored health, and do not address battery
153 or power electronics degradation under real usage over tens of thousands of kilome-
154 ters. To the best of our knowledge, no prior work has treated electric unicycles as
155 everyday vehicles equipped with health and usage monitoring comparable to HUMS
156 in other transport domains, nor has any study exploited real-world EUC logs over tens
157 of thousands of kilometers to jointly monitor battery and power electronics health.

160 2.2 Micromobility, climate and safety

161 Micromobility devices such as e-scooters, e-bikes and other PEVs are increasingly pro-
162 moted as low-carbon alternatives to private cars for short and medium-distance trips,
163 with potential benefits in terms of greenhouse gas emissions, local air pollution and
164 congestion when they effectively replace motorized trips [2, 3]. Life-cycle assessments of
165 shared and private micromobility services show that their environmental performance
166 is highly sensitive to vehicle lifetime, utilisation and operational practices; longer-lived
167 devices with high mileage and low empty rebalancing tend to offer the largest cli-
168 mate benefits [11, 24]. Electric unicycles, with their low vehicle mass relative to the
169 rider and high energy efficiency per kilometre, have the potential to fit particularly
170 well into this picture, although they are rarely considered explicitly in micromobility
171 environmental assessments.

172 From a safety perspective, national and international reports document a marked
173 increase in crashes, serious injuries and fatalities involving micromobility users since
174 2019 without a proper breakdown by PEV category [1–3] as discussed in Section 1.
175 Most policy and research efforts to date have focused on infrastructure, speed regula-
176 tion, user behaviour and protective equipment, while the internal health of the vehicles
177 themselves has received comparatively little attention. In particular, there is no sys-
178 tematic assessment of how long-term degradation of batteries and power electronics
179 might affect the risk of loss-of-power events for micromobility vehicles, despite the fact
180 that these devices are increasingly sensorised and connected.

181 Current regulatory approaches to micromobility have largely emphasized speed
182 limits, access rules and equipment requirements, often with limited empirical insight
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into how these measures interact with the technical reliability and degradation of the vehicles themselves. A more integrated perspective that combines infrastructure, user behaviour and vehicle health could help move beyond purely heuristic rules.

2.3 Health and usage monitoring systems for vehicles

In contrast, Health and Usage Monitoring Systems (HUMS) and related vehicle health monitoring systems have been widely studied and deployed in other transport domains. In aerospace and military land vehicles, HUMS architectures combine on-board sensing, data logging and diagnostic algorithms to monitor critical subsystems, support condition-based maintenance and reduce unexpected failures [4–7]. Recent work on vehicular sensor networks and data analytics further emphasizes the role of long-term usage data and prognostic indicators in managing fleets of safety-critical vehicles [4].

Despite conceptual similarities between micromobility vehicles and other electric vehicles in terms of energy storage and powertrain architecture, we are not aware of any HUMS-like framework specifically designed for electric unicycles or other EDPMs. Existing micromobility deployments typically log trips for billing and basic statistics, but do not implement systematic health indicators for the battery pack or power electronics, nor do they leverage long-term field data to characterize degradation at the vehicle level. This gap motivates the development of vehicle-level health and usage monitoring tools tailored to the constraints and data channels of commercially available EUCs.

2.4 Battery and power electronics health monitoring from field data

For lithium-ion batteries, a substantial body of work has investigated state-of-health estimation and fault detection using field data from electric vehicles, stationary storage systems and dedicated test benches. Internal resistance, voltage sag under load and derived features have been repeatedly identified as informative health indicators, especially when analyzed under comparable operating conditions [8–11]. Recent studies have highlighted the presence of “elbows” or “knees” in ageing trajectories, corresponding to regimes of accelerated degradation and rapid loss of performance, and have explored data-driven methods for detecting abnormal SoH estimates and battery faults in large fleets of electric vehicles [12, 13, 25–29].

In parallel, power MOSFETs and other power devices have been the subject of extensive reliability and condition-monitoring research. Variations of on-state resistance, junction temperature and related electrical parameters have been used as precursors of degradation under thermal cycling and accelerated ageing, and have enabled remaining useful life estimation in controlled experiments [14–19]. However, most of these studies target automotive inverters, power modules or individual battery packs, and are not integrated into a vehicle-level health and usage monitoring framework for micromobility devices. To the best of our knowledge, no prior work has exploited long-term EUC ride logs over tens of thousands of kilometers to jointly monitor the health of the battery pack and the power MOSFET stage, and to relate their evolution to vehicle-level safety margins.

231 3 System description and methods

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233 The datasets and source code used to generate the results of this paper are openly avail-
234 able at the EUC_SOH Zenodo repository (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19024289>),
235 with EUC brands/models and personally identifying information removed from the
236 logs.

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238 3.1 Telemetry and log structure

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240 EUC_SOH operates on ride logs exported from user-facing applications such as EUC
241 World or WheelLog. Each log corresponds to a single ride and contains timestamped
242 samples of pack voltage, battery current, vehicle speed and, when available, board and
243 motor temperatures and phase current. For each wheel, we consider a collection of
244 CSV logs covering several hundreds to thousands of kilometers, and we use the wheel
245 odometer value recorded in each file to position every ride on the lifetime axis.

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247 Within each log, we focus on periods of high load where the vehicle is simulta-
248 neously moving and drawing significant current. Concretely, we retain samples that
249 satisfy a speed threshold (typically 20 km/h) and an adaptive threshold on the abso-
250 lute battery current, and discard low-load segments (near-idle coasting or very low
251 current). This selection aims to approximate quasi-steady high-load conditions where
252 voltage sag and Joule losses are most informative about the combined health of the
253 battery and power electronics.

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254 3.2 Equivalent resistance and global health indicator

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256 For each log, EUC_SOH first identifies quasi-idle segments where the vehicle is moving
257 slowly or not at all and the battery current remains close to zero. On these segments,
258 it estimates a local idle pack voltage V_{idle} as a high percentile (typically 95th) of the
259 measured voltage at very low current. When a reliable voltage-based state-of-charge
260 (SoC) proxy is available for the wheel (inferred from the maximum pack voltage,
261 number of series cells and near-full resting voltage), these quasi-idle plateaus are also
262 associated with an approximate SoC value, and a piecewise-linear profile $V_{\text{idle}}(\text{SoC})$ is
263 constructed from them. For any sample in the log, a local idle voltage $V_{\text{idle,local}}$ is then
264 obtained either by evaluating this profile at the corresponding SoC or, when such a
265 profile cannot be built, by falling back to an average of the quasi-idle voltages.

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266 Using this local reference, EUC_SOH focuses on periods of high load where the
267 vehicle is simultaneously moving and drawing significant current. Concretely, we retain
268 samples that satisfy a speed threshold (typically 20 km/h) and a current window
269 adapted to the pack voltage (with a minimum threshold; if too few points are found,
270 the window is widened), and we optionally restrict the analysis to mid-range SoC (e.g.
271 between 20% and 90%) when SoC information is available. For every retained high-
272 load sample with measured voltage V and current I , we compute the instantaneous
273 voltage sag and equivalent resistance as

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$$\text{sag} = V_{\text{idle,local}} - V, \quad R_{\text{eq}} = \frac{\text{sag}}{|I|}.$$

We then aggregate these pointwise values at the log level using the median and the 95th percentile:

- `Req_median`: median of R_{eq} over high-load samples;
- `Req_95p`: 95th percentile of R_{eq} .

`Req_median` is used as the main global health indicator for the energy and power stages combined (battery, MOSFETs and wiring). Numerous studies have shown that DC internal resistance and voltage sag increase with ageing and closely track capacity fade and performance loss in lithium-ion batteries, especially in the early and mid-life regions [8–11, 24]. By construction, `Req_median` captures the dominant ohmic contribution of the pack under representative load conditions for each ride, while the use of a local $V_{idle,local}$ profile reduces the bias that would arise from large state-of-charge swings within a single log.

It is important to emphasize that R_{eq} and `Req_median` are *pack-level indicators* rather than direct estimates of a specific electrochemical parameter. They lump together the ohmic contributions of battery cells, busbars, connectors and power devices, and they are inferred under dynamic load and finite sampling frequency, not under controlled laboratory DC conditions. As such, they should be interpreted primarily as relative indicators within the history of a given wheel, under comparable operating conditions, rather than as precise absolute measurements of cell-level internal resistance. This empirical nature is unavoidable given the limited telemetry exposed by commercially available EUCs, but it remains sufficient for detecting large intra-wheel drifts and out-of-family behaviour.

3.3 Separating battery and MOSFET contributions

When additional information about the power stage is available (e.g. datasheet or measured values), `EUC_SOH` can separate the contributions of the battery and the MOSFET bridge to the measured equivalent resistance. The user provides:

- a total on-state resistance $R_{ds,on,25^{\circ}C}$ for the full MOSFET bridge at $25^{\circ}C$;
- a relative thermal coefficient α describing the variation of $R_{ds,on}$ with junction or board temperature;
- an optional wiring/busbar resistance R_{wiring} .

Using the maximum board/controller temperature `temp_board_max` recorded in each log as a proxy for the MOSFET junction temperature, we estimate the hot MOSFET resistance as

$$R_{MOSFET,hot} = R_{ds,on,25^{\circ}C} \cdot (1 + \alpha \cdot (T_{board} - 25)) + R_{wiring}.$$

We then obtain a battery-only median resistance estimate by subtracting this contribution from the global median:

$$R_{batt,median} = \max(0, R_{eq,median} - R_{MOSFET,hot}),$$

323 and we normalize battery resistance to 25°C using an Arrhenius correction to obtain
324 `R_batt_median_25C`.

325 **Temperature proxy caveat.** All temperature-dependent corrections in `EUC_SOH`
326 rely on `temp_board_max`, the maximum temperature of the main board/controller
327 recorded during a ride, as the sole thermal observable. This quantity is a coarse proxy:
328 it reflects the thermal state of the controller PCB, not the junction temperature of
329 individual MOSFETs, the surface temperature of battery cells, or the ambient tem-
330 perature. The board sensor is also read at the logging frequency of the companion app
331 (typically 1–10 Hz), so transient thermal peaks at the device level are not captured. As
332 a consequence, $R_{\text{MOSFET,hot}}$ and the Arrhenius-corrected `R_batt_median_25C` should
333 be interpreted as empirical, intra-wheel de-seasoning estimates rather than as phys-
334 ically exact thermal corrections. They remain useful for tracking relative changes
335 within the history of a given wheel, but are not suitable for precise cross-wheel or
336 cross-platform comparisons without additional thermal calibration.

337 This decomposition yields three interpretable indicators per log: `Req_median`
338 (global), `R_mosfet_hot` (power stage), and `R_batt_median / R_batt_median_25C`
339 (battery-dominated). The separation is approximate and relies on simplified thermal
340 and electrical models, but it is consistent with prior work using on-state resistance drift
341 as a precursor of MOSFET degradation and DC resistance growth as an indicator of
342 battery ageing [8–12, 14–19]. Accordingly, we only use these indicators to track rela-
343 tive intra-wheel changes and to provide qualitative insight into whether observed drifts
344 are more compatible with battery-dominated or power-stage-dominated scenarios.

346 3.4 Additional indicators: sag, current, temperature and 347 phase current 348

349 Beyond equivalent resistance, `EUC_SOH` computes several complementary indicators
350 for each log:

- 351 • `sag_95p`, `sag_max`: 95th percentile and maximum of voltage sag under load,
352 capturing worst-case ohmic drops and their evolution over time;
- 353 • `v_min_strong`: minimum voltage reached under high-load conditions, reflecting the
354 remaining safety margin before low-voltage cut-off, for a given SoC and temperature;
- 355 • `i_95p`, `i_max`: 95th percentile and maximum battery current, characterizing typical
356 and extreme electrical stress on the pack;
- 357 • `temp_board_max`: maximum board/controller temperature, used as a proxy for
358 MOSFET thermal stress;
- 359 • `temp_motor_max`: maximum motor temperature, when available.

361 When firmware provides a phase current signal, we also compute:

- 362 • `i_phase_max`, `i_phase_95p`: maximum and 95th percentile of phase current;
- 363 • `I_phase2_int`: the phase-current stress density, defined as

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$$I_{\text{phase2_int}} = \frac{\int_{t_{\text{start}}}^{t_{\text{end}}} I_{\text{phase}}^2(t) dt}{T_{\text{ride}}}, \quad T_{\text{ride}} = t_{\text{end}} - t_{\text{start}},$$

expressed in A^2 (dimension of a mean squared current). When the ride duration T_{ride} cannot be inferred from the log timestamps, a fixed sampling interval of 0.1s is used as a fallback and the raw integral $A^2 \cdot s$ is retained without normalisation.

The normalization by T_{ride} makes `I_phase2_int` comparable across rides of different durations: a long ride at moderate current and a short ride at high current producing the same thermal burden per unit time will yield the same value, whereas the un-normalized integral would unfairly penalize longer rides. This quantity acts as a proxy for the mean power dissipated in the MOSFETs, shunts and motor windings per unit time, and thus for the sustained thermal stress applied to the power stage during the ride. This is in line with fatigue and power-cycling studies of power semiconductors, where accumulated I^2t and thermal cycling are key drivers of degradation [14, 15, 18].

The integral $\int I_{\text{phase}}^2 dt$ acts as a proxy for the total Joule energy dissipated in the MOSFETs, shunts and motor windings during the ride, and thus for the cumulative thermal stress applied to the power stage. This is in line with fatigue and power-cycling studies of power semiconductors, where accumulated I^2t and thermal cycling are key drivers of degradation [14, 15, 18].

3.5 Statistical reference and alarm thresholds

For confidentiality and to avoid brand-specific controversy, individual EUCs are anonymized as Wheel B, Wheel E, etc., and manufacturer/model names are not disclosed.

The statistical reference is built from each wheel’s own history, using either the full log set or a low-resistance fraction as the reference subset. This approach relies on the empirically supported assumption that Li-ion and MOSFET degradation produces distinct regime changes (elbows/knees) rather than imperceptibly slow continuous drift [12, 13, 15]. Under this assumption, late-life degraded logs represent a small fraction of the total dataset, and their inclusion in the reference has limited influence on the estimated mean and standard deviation as confirmed empirically in our case studies, where late-life values exceed the danger threshold by several α even when computed on the full log set.

This behaviour is illustrated in Appendix A2, where strong synthetic late-life deviations on `Req_median` for `Wheel_P_bad` remain a small fraction of the dataset and do not materially alter the per-wheel Gaussian bands.

On this set, we compute a mean μ and standard deviation σ for each metric. We then define:

- a green band $[\mu - 1\sigma, \mu + 1\sigma]$ representing the normal range;
- an orange band between the green band and a danger threshold;
- a danger threshold at $\mu + 2\sigma$ for metrics where higher values are worse (resistances, sag, temperatures, currents), and $\mu - 2\sigma$ for metrics where lower values are worse (minimum voltage).

Measurement uncertainty in pack voltage and current is not specified by EUC manufacturers or companion apps. In the absence of public specifications, we assume that embedded sensors exhibit relative errors in the range of 2-5% for both voltage and

415 current, which is consistent with the accuracy reported for typical automotive-grade
416 Hall and shunt sensors and with field observations of pack-voltage calibration offsets
417 reported by EUC users. Under these assumptions, a first-order error propagation on
418 $R_{\text{eq}} = \text{sag}/|I|$ yields a relative uncertainty on individual R_{eq} samples on the order of
419 3–7%, depending on the operating point.

420 Two mechanisms mitigate the impact of this uncertainty on the diagnostic indi-
421 cators used here. First, each per-log metric such as `Req_median`, `Req_95p` or `sag_95p`
422 aggregates hundreds of high-load samples within a ride; random measurement noise
423 therefore averages out and affects the per-log statistics far less than the raw sample-
424 level values. Second, the degradation patterns of interest in this work correspond to
425 large-amplitude changes in these metrics: in the synthetic ageing scenarios, equivalent
426 and battery resistance roughly double between early life and late-life regimes, while
427 in the real data the largest deviations from baseline amount to several standard devi-
428 ations of the per-wheel reference. These amplitudes exceed the assumed instrumental
429 uncertainty by at least one order of magnitude.

430 Systematic biases in voltage and current measurements, which are fixed for a given
431 wheel, cancel in intra-wheel comparisons and only affect cross-wheel comparisons.
432 Since `EUC_SOH` is explicitly designed to use each wheel as its own reference, and
433 we do not attempt to compare absolute resistance levels between different models,
434 the conclusions of this study are robust to such biases. A more detailed Monte Carlo
435 treatment of measurement error would therefore not materially change the diagnostic
436 conclusions for the drift magnitudes considered here; the dominant source of log-to-log
437 variability remains the diversity of operating conditions (ambient temperature, SoC,
438 load profile) rather than instrumental noise.

439 For cases where the initial state is already degraded (e.g. second-hand vehicle),
440 a complementary absolute alarm based on `R_pack_nominal` provides a usage-context-
441 independent safety net.

442 A summary alarm table lists the logs that exceed these thresholds, together with
443 their values and deviations from the reference. Similar Gaussian-threshold approaches
444 are widely used for anomaly detection in battery packs and quality control, with the
445 usual caveats regarding non-Gaussian distributions and the choice of the reference
446 sample [10, 24, 25, 28, 30].

447 In addition to these statistical thresholds, `EUC_SOH` applies an absolute rule on
448 `Req_median`. A nominal pack resistance is estimated from the inferred number of series
449 cells (based on maximum pack voltage) and typical cell resistance values from public
450 data for 18650/21700 chemistries, and an alarm is raised if `Req_median` exceeds a
451 configurable multiple of this nominal (e.g. 1.8×) beyond a given mileage tuned so that
452 it flags clearly abnormal but not borderline cases on the wheels considered. The goal
453 is to flag objectively high resistances even if the local statistics have “normalized” an
454 already degraded pack.

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456 3.6 Trend and change detection

457 To characterize long-term degradation and detect regime changes, `EUC_SOH` couples
458 the above indicators with simple trend and change-detection mechanisms. For selected
459 metrics (e.g. `R_batt_median_25C`, `R_mosfet_hot`, `Req_median`, `sag_95p`), we fit linear
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trends as a function of wheel mileage and report slopes to quantify statistically significant increases. We also apply a one-sided cumulative sum (CUSUM) change detector to these time series, using an early-life subset of logs as a reference and monitoring the remaining logs for sustained shifts in the mean. In addition to per-metric CUSUM, EUC_SOH performs a simple regime classification at the wheel level. Using the cumulative mileage and the outputs of the change detectors on resistance and sag indicators, we label intervals of the life trajectory as “slow” or “accelerated” regimes, corresponding respectively to baseline ageing and statistically significant steps in degradation. These labels are used only for presentation purposes in the reports (e.g. annotating plots with a “Slow regime” background) and do not affect the underlying health metrics or alarm thresholds. This combination of regression-based trend analysis, Gaussian thresholds and CUSUM is intended to provide transparent, interpretable signals of degradation and abnormal behaviour, rather than a single black-box decision. In the experimental section, we illustrate how these methods highlight both gradual resistance increases over tens of thousands of kilometers and isolated, large out-of-family events on individual logs.

For CUSUM-based change detection, we use a simple, fixed parametrisation across wheels and metrics. For each metric m , the reference mean μ_{ref} and standard deviation σ_{ref} are computed on the first 30% of the lifetime in mileage, which we treat as an early-life healthy baseline. A one-sided CUSUM for upward shifts (“higher is worse”) is then applied to the remaining logs, with decision level h corresponding to $\mu_{\text{ref}} + 3\sigma_{\text{ref}}$ (Fig. A1), and an intermediate line at $\mu_{\text{ref}} + 1.5\sigma_{\text{ref}}$ used for visualisation only.

This parametrisation follows standard statistical process control practice, where CUSUM thresholds at 3σ above the in-control mean provide a transparent compromise between robustness to noise and sensitivity to sustained shifts. In our case studies, the detected change points on resistance and sag metrics were stable when varying the reference fraction between 20% and 40% of the mileage span and when shifting h between $2.5\sigma_{\text{ref}}$ and $3.5\sigma_{\text{ref}}$, so we keep the same values for all wheels to favour simplicity and interpretability.

Linear trends are fitted by ordinary least squares on each metric as a function of mileage. For the indicators highlighted in Section 4 (battery resistance at 25°C, global equivalent resistance and 95th-percentile sag), the estimated slopes are positive and the corresponding p-values are well below 0.01, even when subsampling the data by a factor of two. We therefore report only the slope magnitudes in the plots, as the statistical significance of the trends is not in doubt for the datasets considered.

3.7 Aging simulator and synthetic ride logs

In addition to analysing real ride logs, we designed an ageing simulator to generate synthetic SoH trajectories and corresponding WheelLog-like files. The goal of this simulator is not to reproduce the full multi-physics coupling of electrochemical, thermal and mechanical phenomena in lithium-ion batteries or power devices, but to provide *stylized, statistically consistent* scenarios that stress-test the EUC_SOH indicators and detection mechanisms. In particular, the simulator focuses on reproducing plausible long-term trends and accelerated degradation regimes (“knees” or “elbows”) in the

507 *observed indicators themselves* (equivalent resistance, sag, thermal proxies, current-
508 stress measures), while preserving the marginal distributions and correlations seen in
509 a given real wheel.

510 Starting from a real wheel folder, we first compute per-log health indicators and
511 Gaussian alarm thresholds as described in Section 3.5 (means, standard deviations and
512 directions “higher_is_bad” or “lower_is_bad”). These thresholds are used as a statistical
513 prior for each metric m in the set

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515 $\{Req_median, Req_95p, sag_95p, sag_max, v_min_strong, i_max, i_95p,$
516 $i_phase_95p, i_phase_max, I_phase2_int, temp_board_max, temp_motor_max,$
517 $R_batt_median, R_mosfet_hot\}$

518
519 Given a synthetic mileage trajectory $\{k_i\}_{i=1}^N$ over several years (e.g. weekly steps
520 of 100 km), the simulator generates a value series $m(k_i)$ for each indicator. For each
521 metric, we use:

- 522 • the empirical mean μ_m and standard deviation σ_m from the real-wheel reference as
523 a baseline;
- 524 • a target offset of the order of $\alpha\sigma_m$ at the end of life (with α configurable),
525 representing the total magnitude of degradation in that metric;
- 526 • a two-stage drift model with a slow linear increase over most of the mileage span
527 and a faster increase after a knee point at a fraction k_{knee} of the mileage (typically
528 90% of the span), mimicking the transition to accelerated ageing observed in real
529 batteries [12, 13];
- 530 • additive noise with variance smaller than σ_m^2 , to reflect intra-log variability without
531 hiding the long-term trend.

532
533 We distinguish battery-related metrics (`Req_median`, `Req_95p`, `R_batt_median`,
534 `sag_95p`, `sag_max`) from power-electronics-related metrics (`R_mosfet_hot`,
535 `temp_board_max`, `i_phase_95p`, `i_phase_max`, `I_phase2_int`) and allow different
536 simulation modes:

- 537 • *global*: all metrics drift with comparable magnitude;
- 538 • *batt_only*: battery metrics exhibit a strong, clearly visible drift, while MOSFET
539 metrics remain almost flat;
- 540 • *mosfet_only*: MOSFET-related metrics drift significantly, while battery metrics
541 change very little.

542
543 In *batt_only* mode, for instance, the final offset for battery metrics is scaled up and
544 forced to be positive (higher resistance and sag), while MOSFET metrics are given
545 a very small drift. For metrics where lower values are worse (e.g. `v_min_strong`), the
546 drift sign is adjusted to respect the “higher_is_bad” / “lower_is_bad” convention.

547 Because the simulator operates at the level of the derived indicators rather than
548 at the level of detailed electrochemical state variables, the resulting synthetic tra-
549 jectories should be interpreted as *what-if* scenarios for the EUC_SOH pipeline: they
550 answer questions of the form “*if this wheel’s equivalent resistance and sag doubled*
551 *over 30 000 km according to a knee-like pattern, would the monitoring system detect*
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it?”, rather than providing quantitative predictions of real-world ageing paths. This abstraction is deliberate: it allows us to evaluate the sensitivity and specificity of the proposed indicators and change detectors under controlled, high-contrast degradation patterns, without claiming high-fidelity physical ageing simulation.

The result of this process is a synthetic SoH summary table with one row per synthetic ride, containing the wheel mileage, a timestamp, and all simulated metrics. To obtain full ride logs compatible with the real analysis pipeline, we then generate WheelLog-like CSV files whose internal samples are consistent with the synthetic metrics. For each synthetic log, we:

- choose a ride duration and number of samples, and generate realistic profiles of speed and battery current (with phase current derived as a speed-dependent multiple of battery current);
- construct a voltage time series such that the median equivalent resistance matches the target `Req_median` and the high-percentile sag matches `sag_95p`;
- simulate board and motor temperature dynamics using simple first-order thermal models driven by I^2 , and rescale the resulting trajectories so that their maxima match the target `temp_board_max` and `temp_motor_max`.

This procedure yields synthetic WheelLog folders that can be processed by EUC_SOH exactly like real data. In Section 4, we use these synthetic datasets to create controlled scenarios of global degradation, battery-only degradation and MOSFET-only degradation, and to evaluate the sensitivity and specificity of our trend and anomaly detection mechanisms under known ground-truth conditions.

4 Results

4.1 Long-term monitoring on a healthy EUC

We first illustrate EUC_SOH on an electric unicycle monitored from about 400 km to 7800 km of wheel mileage. The corresponding summary charts in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 show resp. the evolution of `Req_median`, `R_batt_median_25C`, `R_mosfet_hot` and `sag_95p` and the evolution of `temp_board_max`, `I_phase2_int`, `i_95p` and `i_max` as a function of wheel mileage for a set of rides covering roughly one year of use. The green bands and red danger thresholds are computed from the EUC history itself using the Gaussian reference procedure described in Section 3.5.

For this wheel, all resistance-based indicators remain within or close to the green bands over the observation window. `Req_median` and `R_batt_median_25C` exhibit only modest fluctuations around their reference values, without any clear upward trend or approach to the danger thresholds. The MOSFET-related resistance `R_mosfet_hot` remains close to its nominal range, and the voltage sag metrics `sag_95p` and `sag_max` stay well below their danger thresholds, indicating stable ohmic behaviour of the energy and power stages. Battery current percentiles and maximums, as well as board and motor temperatures, also remain within expected ranges given the usage patterns, with no alarming excursions.

This case demonstrates that EUC_SOH can characterize a wheel operating in a healthy regime over more than 7000 km of additional mileage, providing a compact

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610 (a) Median equivalent pack resistance R_{eq_median} vs wheel mileage for Wheel P (intra-wheel indicator combining battery and power stage).

611 (b) Battery-dominated pack resistance $R_{batt,median@25^{\circ}C}$ vs wheel mileage for Wheel P (intra-wheel indicator normalised to $25^{\circ}C$).

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627 (c) MOSFET + wiring resistance proxy $R_{mosfet,hot}$ vs wheel mileage for Wheel P (estimated from board-temperature proxy).

628 (d) 95th-percentile voltage sag $sag_{95\%}$ vs wheel mileage for Wheel P under high-load conditions.

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Fig. 1: EUC_SOH pack-level health indicators for Wheel P over its monitored lifetime. All curves are intra-wheel, using this wheel as its own reference, and combine the effects of battery, power stage and wiring under the data and thermal-proxy limitations described in Section 3.5.

view of stability in both battery and power electronics indicators. For such a wheel, the alarm table 1 remains sparse and mostly highlights isolated rides with slightly higher stress, which can be interpreted as normal variation rather than signs of degradation.

Yet, the last ride on the monitored wheel P illustrates the interest of monitoring those machines for safety purposes. For, during that run, the rider reported no obvious symptoms at the vehicle level (no tilt-back, no audible alarms, no over-temperature warnings), and the ride felt subjectively “normal”. In the EUC_SOH analysis, however,

(a) Maximum board/controller temperature `temp_board_max` vs wheel mileage for Wheel P (proxy for power-stage thermal stress).

(b) Phase-current stress density `I_phase2_int` vs wheel mileage for Wheel P (mean I^2 over ride duration, proxy for sustained electrothermal stress).

(c) Battery current 95th percentile `i_95p` vs wheel mileage for Wheel P.

(d) Maximum battery current `i_max` vs wheel mileage for Wheel P.

Fig. 2: Thermal and current-stress indicators for Wheel P over its monitored lifetime (intra-wheel view). These indicators characterise the typical and extreme electrical and thermal loading experienced by the power stage and are used to contextualise the resistance and sag trends in Fig. 1.

the corresponding log sits near the top of the wheel’s historical distribution for electrical stress: both the 95th-percentile and maximum battery currents exceed the wheel’s internal danger thresholds, while phase-current stress as measured by the `i_phase_95p` and `i_phase_max` in Fig. 3 is among the highest values observed for this wheel, even though resistance and sag metrics remain within their nominal ranges. In other words, the session was significantly more demanding on the power stage than typical rides, without any immediate feedback from the wheel itself. This type of situation motivates the use of long-term, log-based health and usage monitoring: it is precisely when the

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691 vehicle still behaves “normally” that riders are most likely to accumulate high-stress
 692 runs without realizing how hard they are driving the hardware.

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706 (a) Phase current 95th percentile
 707 $i_{\text{phase_95p}}$ vs wheel mileage for Wheel P
 708 (proxy for typical MOSFET and winding
 709 current stress).

710 (b) Maximum phase current $i_{\text{phase_max}}$
 711 vs wheel mileage for Wheel P (proxy for
 712 extreme MOSFET and winding loading).

710 **Fig. 3:** Phase-current-based stress indicators for Wheel P over its monitored lifetime
 711 (intra-wheel view). These quantities do not model junction temperature explicitly, but
 712 act as empirical proxies for the electrical loading experienced by the MOSFET bridge
 713 and motor windings in the absence of device-level thermal measurements.

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Table 1: Alarmed logs for Wheel P : mileage and compact alarm reasons.

Wheel km	Alarm reasons (compact)
418.8	high $R_{\text{eq,med}}$, high phase $I_{95\%}$
3946.3	huge R_{eq} (med, 95%), sag \uparrow (95%, max), low V_{min} , high R_{batt}
4542.0	huge R_{eq} (med, 95%), sag \uparrow (95%, max), low V_{min} , high R_{batt}
4655.6	huge R_{eq} (med, 95%), sag \uparrow (95%, max), low V_{min} , high R_{batt}
4792.6	$R_{\text{eq,med}}\uparrow$, $R_{\text{batt}}\uparrow$ (moderate)
7479.0	$R_{\text{eq}}\uparrow$ (med, 95%), sag \uparrow (95%, max), $R_{\text{batt}}\uparrow$
7685.0	$R_{\text{eq}}\uparrow$ (med, 95%), sag \uparrow 95%, $R_{\text{batt}}\uparrow$
7703.8	$R_{\text{eq}}\uparrow$ (med, 95%), sag \uparrow (95%, max), $R_{\text{batt}}\uparrow$

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4.2 Simulated progressive degradation on Wheel P (Wheel_P_bad)

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We next consider a synthetic ageing scenario derived from the same EUC wheel P. Using the aging simulator described in Section 3.7, we generate a synthetic SoH

(a) Median equivalent pack resistance R_{eq_median} vs wheel mileage for the synthetic Wheel_P_bad trajectory (stylized ageing scenario).

(b) Battery-dominated pack resistance $R_{batt,median@25^{\circ}C}$ vs wheel mileage for Wheel_P_bad.

(c) MOSFET + wiring resistance proxy $R_{mosfet,hot}$ vs wheel mileage for Wheel_P_bad.

(d) 95th-percentile voltage sag $sag_{95\%}$ vs wheel mileage for Wheel_P_bad under high-load conditions.

Fig. 4: stylized synthetic ageing scenario for Wheel P (Wheel_P_bad). The synthetic indicators are constructed by amplifying late-life trends in the real wheel’s pack-level metrics to emulate a knee-like degradation pattern, while preserving early-life behaviour. These trajectories are used to stress-test the EUC_SOH indicators and change detectors rather than to predict a specific physical ageing path.

trajectory over approximately 30-35 000 km. This data is created with controlled, progressive degradation affecting both battery and MOSFET-related indicators (mode *global*). The corresponding Wheel_P_bad report shows clear increasing trends in $R_{batt,median.25C}$, R_{mosfet_hot} , R_{eq_median} and sag_{95p} as mileage increases, as shown in Fig. 4.

For Wheel P, histograms of R_{eq_median} (Fig. A1) show that the synthetic trajectory remains within the empirical range of the real wheel in the early-life region, while its late-life tail extends several standard deviations above the reference, as intended by the degradation model.

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783 Linear trend fits yield positive slopes on all four indicators, with
 784 `R_batt_median_25C` showing a slope on the order of $10^{-2} \Omega/1000 \text{ km}$, which reflects a
 785 sustained increase in both battery and global equivalent resistance.

786 Change-point detection on `R_batt_median_25C`, `R_mosfet_hot`, `Req_median` and
 787 `sag_95p` shows clear late-life regime shifts, with the cumulative sums crossing the
 788 decision thresholds consistently with the accelerated degradation imposed by the
 789 simulator, *cf.* Appendix A.3.

790 In parallel, Table 2 shows that in the last 5 000 km of the synthetic trajectory, most
 791 rides are flagged as *danger* on `Req_median`, `R_batt_median_25C` and `sag_95p`. Also
 792 `v_min_strong` approaches the low-voltage danger threshold, reflecting a substantial
 793 loss of electrical margin compared to the real Wheel P reference.

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797 **Table 2:** Synthetic Wheel P: Selected alarmed logs at early and late mileage (compact
 798 alarm reasons).

799	Wheel km	Alarm reasons (compact)
800	10 455	motor T_{\max} slightly above limit
801	11 955	high phase I^2 dose
802	12 655–13 255	sparse motor T_{\max} , phase $I_{95\%}$ alarms
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804	33 255	huge R_{eq} (med, 95%), sag \uparrow (95%, max), low V_{\min} , high R_{batt} , high board T_{\max}
805	33 355	huge R_{eq} (med, 95%), sag \uparrow (95%, max), low V_{\min} , high R_{batt} , high board T_{\max}
806	33 455–33 755	same pattern, with further increase in R_{batt} , R_{mosfet} , sag and board temperature

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809 Because the synthetic trajectories are constructed so that the final offsets corre-
 810 spond to several standard deviations of the real Wheel P reference, we can treat this
 811 scenario as a controlled positive test for the detection mechanisms. The results indicate
 812 that EUC_SOH correctly identifies long-term drift in both battery and MOSFET-
 813 related indicators, in this synthetic scenario. It raises alarms when resistance and sag
 814 enter clearly abnormal regimes, and provides interpretable diagnostics in terms of
 815 gradual loss of margin.

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4.3 Detection of a single major deviation on a long-life wheel (Wheel S)

819 Finally, we examine a synthetic scenario based on EUC named wheel S with a life-
 820 time of real data extended synthetically to about 26 000-27 000 km. For most of the
 821 mileage range, the `Wheel_S.bad` report shows a slow, regular evolution of `Req_median`,
 822 `R_batt_median_25C`, `R_mosfet_hot` and sag metrics, all remaining within the green
 823 band or slightly above, consistent with a “slow ageing” regime. In this regime, only
 824 a limited number of logs cross the danger thresholds, and the alarm table remains
 825 relatively sparse.

826 Near the end of the mileage range, a single synthetic log (e.g. around 26 000-
 827 27 000 km) is constructed to exhibit a large, abrupt degradation in a single indicator
 828 : `R_mosfet_hot` jumps to values well above its danger thresholds. As shown in Fig. 5

Board temperature also reaches unusually high values for this wheel, reflecting severe stress on the power stage.

(a) MOSFET + wiring resistance proxy $R_{\text{mosfet,hot}}$ vs wheel mileage for synthetic Wheel S, with a single injected late-life step. (b) Maximum board/controller temperature temp_board_max vs wheel mileage for the same synthetic trajectory.

Fig. 5: Detection of a single major event on linked indicators for synthetic Wheel S. A stylized step change is injected in the MOSFET-dominated resistance proxy and associated board temperature to emulate a sudden degradation or partial failure. EUC_SOH is used here to illustrate how such out-of-family events would appear in the pack-level indicators under the constraints of EUC telemetry.

EUC_SOH flags this log as an out-of-family event across multiple metrics: it appears as an isolated red point in the resistance and temperature plots, well separated from the cloud of previous logs, and is prominently listed in the alarm table with large deviations from the reference. Importantly, this detection occurs even though global statistics (e.g. overall mean and standard deviation across the full life) remain dominated by the long period of normal operation. The method therefore proves capable of highlighting a single major deviation at the end of an otherwise regular trajectory, which is precisely the type of event that could hypothetically precede or coincide with a dangerous loss-of-power incident.

Together, these three cases show that EUC_SOH can (i) confirm stable operation for a healthy wheel, (ii) detect and quantify progressive degradation over tens of thousands of kilometers, and (iii) isolate rare but severe out-of-family events on individual logs in a long-life wheel. In the discussion, we analyse how such information could be used to support maintenance decisions and to better understand safety margins for EUC riders.

Overall, the present study covers three real wheels with monitored mileage ranging from about 900 km to 7 800 km and a total of 43 ride logs, complemented by synthetic trajectories extending individual wheels up to 25 000-35 000 km. While this represents only a small sample of the EUC population, it already spans different usage profiles, with some wheels used mostly for moderate commuting and others exhibiting frequent high-current, high-sag runs.

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875 **5 Discussion**

876 877 **5.1 Implications for EUC safety and usage**

878 The results suggest that long-term monitoring of pack-level resistance, sag and thermal
879 indicators can provide early, interpretable signals of degradation in electric unicycles,
880 even when only user-accessible telemetry is available. On a healthy wheel, EUC_SOH
881 confirms the stability of key indicators over more than 7000 km of additional mileage,
882 while in synthetic ageing scenarios it detects both gradual resistance increases and single,
883 large out-of-family events after tens of thousands of kilometers. In practice, such
884 information could be used to trigger precautionary checks, derating or recommended
885 maintenance when a wheel approaches abnormal regimes in battery or power electronics
886 health, thereby possibly reducing the likelihood of operating a severely degraded
887 vehicle at high load.

888 It is important to emphasize that EUC_SOH is not a crash-prediction system.
889 Current micromobility safety statistics do not distinguish EUC hardware failures from
890 crashes caused by collisions or loss-of-control [1–3], and we do not claim that any
891 specific incident could have been prevented by the proposed monitoring alone. Rather,
892 EUC_SOH provides a way to structure and interpret the health information contained
893 in ride logs, in a form that is comparable to HUMS indicators used in other vehicle
894 classes. In the longer term, systematically logging such health indicators alongside
895 incident reports could help build the data needed to understand if and how component
896 degradation contributes to loss-of-power risk in real fleets.

897 898 **5.2 Positioning relative to existing HUMS and EV analytics**

899 From an architectural standpoint, EUC_SOH mirrors key elements of Health and
900 Usage Monitoring Systems: on-board sensing, ride-level feature extraction, statistical
901 baselining, trend and change detection [4–7]. However, it operates under stricter
902 constraints, relying solely on the telemetry exposed to end-users and without access
903 to internal BMS cell-level measurements or high-frequency switching waveforms. In
904 that sense, it is closer to data-driven EV battery analytics using telematics than to
905 intrusive lab instrumentation [8–11, 25, 28, 29].

906 The proposed framework could be extended to other micromobility devices that
907 expose similar telemetry (e-scooters, e-bikes), but electric unicycles constitute an
908 interesting extreme case: their dynamic stability makes them particularly sensitive to
909 loss-of-power events, while their high performance and relatively open protocols provide
910 rich data streams. EUC_SOH therefore offers a concrete example of how HUMS
911 concepts can be adapted to personal micromobility, and highlights the opportunity
912 for manufacturers and app developers to expose and exploit health indicators beyond
913 simple dashboards.

914 Beyond the three detailed case studies, the ageing simulator was applied systematically
915 to all wheels with sufficient historical data. For each wheel, we generated
916 three synthetic trajectories (battery-only degradation, MOSFET-only degradation and
917 global degradation) using the procedure of Section 3.7, and processed the resulting
918 logs through the same EUC_SOH pipeline. In addition, for Wheel S we created a
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dedicated single outlier scenario to emulate an abrupt late-life MOSFET degradation event. These experiments confirm that the combination of resistance, sag and thermal indicators, together with the Gaussian thresholds and CUSUM-like change detectors, behaves consistently across multiple wheels and ageing modes, while remaining interpretable in terms of battery versus power-stage stress.

Although EUC_SOH is tailored to electric unicycles, most of the underlying ideas are generic to electric powertrains, while a few aspects are EUC-specific.

On the generic side, the method relies on pack-level voltage and current measurements, simple Joule-loss arguments and statistical baselining of resistance, sag, current and temperature indicators over long-term usage. These ingredients are directly applicable to other PEVs and EVs that expose similar telemetry.

On the EUC-specific side, EUC_SOH assumes wheels where only pack-level signals and coarse temperature proxies are available to end-users, with no access to BMS cell-level data or high-frequency inverter waveforms. The idle-voltage extraction based on quasi-idle plateaus and the use of wheel-level odometer mileage as the main ageing axis are design choices that reflect this constraint and the typical logging capabilities of EUC companion apps. Extending the approach to other platforms equipped with richer diagnostics (e.g. per-cell voltages, internal impedance estimates) would mainly require replacing the idle-voltage proxy and resistance decomposition with more direct measurements, while keeping the same high-level workflow (per-ride feature extraction, statistical reference building, trend and change detection).

5.3 Practical implications for manufacturers

Beyond health monitoring itself, the present work also indirectly highlights the role of community-developed logging tools. The ride logs analyzed here exist only because independent developers have reverse-engineered proprietary Bluetooth Low Energy (BLE) frames exposed by EUC manufacturers and implemented third-party applications capable of recording pack-level telemetry over long periods of time. In practice, BLE traffic is broadcast in the clear and will be decoded sooner or later; manufacturers would therefore benefit from (i) converging towards more standardised telemetry payloads across models and brands, and (ii) publishing stable BLE interface contracts so that user-facing applications and diagnostics tools can be implemented without repeated reverse-engineering efforts. Such openness would reduce duplicated work, improve data quality and, ultimately, make it easier to build safety-relevant health and usage monitoring tools on top of EUC telemetry.

5.4 Limitations and future work

Several limitations must be acknowledged. First, the separation between battery and MOSFET contributions relies on simplified thermal and electrical models, and on user-supplied parameters such as $R_{ds,on}$ and its temperature coefficient; errors in these inputs can bias the estimated battery resistance. Second, the statistical baselining assumes that a sufficient number of early-life logs represent a healthy state, and uses Gaussian thresholds that may be suboptimal for skewed or heavy-tailed distributions [10, 28, 30]. While Gaussian bands are only an approximate model of the indicator

967 distributions, the appendix example in Fig. A2 shows that, for the wheels studied,
968 even large late-life deviations form a small enough fraction of the data that they do
969 not destabilize the reference mean and standard deviation. Third, environmental and
970 usage factors (ambient temperature, rider mass, terrain, tire pressure) can significantly
971 affect sag, resistance and temperatures, potentially leading to false positives or false
972 negatives if not accounted for. Moreover, the use of a local $V_{\text{idle,local}}$ profile built from
973 quasi-idle plateaus and, when available, voltage-based SoC information provides only
974 an approximation of the true open-circuit voltage; as a result, resistance metrics are
975 best interpreted as comparative indicators within a given wheel rather than as precise
976 absolute measurements.

977 **For one additional wheel (Wheel M)**, the battery pack was replaced during the
978 observation window at around 750 km, leading to a discontinuity in resistance and sag
979 indicators rather than a smooth ageing trajectory. EUC_SOH reflects this as an abrupt
980 step in `Req_median` and `R_batt_median_25C`, followed by a new stable regime. In this
981 case, the pack was swapped for higher-performance cells: `i_95p` reaches the highest
982 values observed for this wheel while `sag_95p` attains its lowest values, see Appendix B.
983 This suggests that using high-output cells can significantly improve electrical margins
984 for EUCs. While we do not analyse this case in detail here, it illustrates that pack
985 replacement appears in the health indicators as a reset event rather than progressive
986 degradation and should be handled explicitly in long-term fleet studies.

988 **The temperature normalization of battery resistance relies on board-
989 /controller temperature as a proxy.** All temperature-dependent quantities
990 (`R_batt_median_25C`, `R_mosfet_hot`, and the Arrhenius correction) use
991 `temp_board_max` as the sole thermal observable. This quantity is a PCB-level measure-
992 ment and does not represent cell junction or MOSFET junction temperatures. The
993 corrections are therefore primarily intended to improve the comparability of logs from
994 the same wheel across sessions with different ambient and thermal conditions; they
995 are not accurate enough to support precise cross-wheel or cross-platform comparisons
996 without additional thermal calibration.

997 **Beyond these methodological aspects, several avenues for improvement and
998 deployment can be envisioned.** Future work will address the above limitations
999 by (i) incorporating explicit conditioning on temperature, current and speed ranges
1000 in the definition of comparable operating points; (ii) exploring more robust statistical
1001 models for baseline and anomaly detection; and (iii) integrating additional information
1002 when available, such as periodic cell-level snapshots from smart BMSs or external
1003 measurements. On the application side, we plan to develop a mobile or embedded
1004 implementation of EUC_SOH that can provide near-real-time feedback to riders, and
1005 to design an anonymized incident and health indicator registry for EUCs and other
1006 EDPMs. Such a registry would enable the community to relate concrete incidents to
1007 prior health trajectories, and to evaluate systematically whether certain degradation
1008 patterns are associated with increased loss-of-power risk.

1010 **Usage profiles remain an important confounding factor:** two wheels with
1011 healthy hardware but very different riding styles (e.g. conservative commuting versus
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aggressive off-road use) can exhibit markedly different distributions of current and I²-dose indicators while sharing similar resistance and sag baselines. In the present work we partly mitigate this by focusing on within-wheel statistics and by using each wheel as its own reference, but a more systematic treatment of usage heterogeneity across wheels is left for future work.

In the longer term, similar diagnostics could be integrated directly into commercial EUCs. At present, health monitoring for electric unicycles is entirely telemetry-driven and relies on external logging applications and offline post-processing of CSV files. From a system design perspective, manufacturers could embed similar diagnostics directly in the vehicle firmware, at the cost of additional memory and computation resources. A first option would be to integrate additional non-volatile memory and continuously log raw telemetry over a sliding time window, then periodically recompute SoH metrics such as equivalent resistance, voltage sag, and phase-current stress integrals on board. A more resource-efficient option would be to aggregate per-ride statistics in real time (e.g. median equivalent resistance under high load, voltage sag percentiles, $\int I_{\text{phase}}^2 dt$, maximum board and motor temperatures) and only store these compact summaries in flash at the end of each ride, so that SoH becomes an embedded property of the vehicle rather than an ex-situ analysis. Beyond passive monitoring, these embedded SoH metrics could directly drive internal safety policies: for each ride summary, the firmware can associate quantitative health indicators with discrete alarm levels and, on the next power-up, decide whether to authorize normal operation, restrict performance, or refuse to start altogether if recent usage exceeded critical limits, while presenting explicit, interpretable messages to the rider instead of opaque generic fault codes.

While EUC_SOH has been developed and evaluated on electric unicycles, the design choices it embodies: pack-level indicators built from end-user telemetry, intra-vehicle baselining, simple but interpretable change detection, and stylized ageing scenarios for method validation are generic. The same pattern could be applied to other personal electric vehicles that provide access to pack voltage, current, temperature and trip data, with appropriate reparameterization of thresholds and stress metrics. In that sense, EUCs can be seen as an early testbed for micromobility vehicle-level HUMS, rather than an isolated niche.

6 Conclusion

We have presented EUC_SOH, a vehicle-level health and usage monitoring system for electric unicycles based on user-accessible ride logs. By extracting interpretable indicators of equivalent resistance, battery-only resistance, MOSFET resistance, voltage sag, current and temperature from thousands to tens of thousands of kilometers of field data, and by combining them with statistical baselining, trend analysis and change detection, EUC_SOH can characterize stable operation, detect progressive degradation and isolate rare but severe out-of-family events in both synthetic and real-world scenarios. Although it does not replace formal safety certification or crash analysis, the proposed framework demonstrates that EUCs can be monitored as serious vehicles

1059 with structured health indicators, and provides a foundation for bringing HUMS-like
1060 practices into the micromobility domain.

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Appendix A Wheel P

A.1 Synthetic data consistency

Fig. A1: Distribution of median equivalent resistance Req_{median} for the real Wheel P (blue, up to its maximum observed mileage) and the synthetic Wheel_P_bad trajectory (orange, full simulated lifetime). The synthetic data preserve the early-life range of the real wheel while adding a late-life tail of higher resistances corresponding to the controlled degradation scenario.

A.2 Gaussian stability under large deviations

A.3 CUSUM detection

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Fig. A2: Median equivalent pack resistance `Req_median` for `Wheel.P_bad` with per-wheel Gaussian bands ($\mu \pm 1\sigma$ and $\mu + 2\sigma$) built from the full history. The late-life synthetic degradation produces strong out-of-family deviations, but these points form a small fraction of the dataset and have limited influence on the estimated mean and standard deviation, illustrating the robustness of the Gaussian reference to a modest number of large deviations.

(a) Median equivalent pack resistance R_{eq_median} with CUSUM-based change detection for Wheel_P_bad.

(b) Battery-dominated pack resistance $R_{batt_median@25^\circ C}$ with CUSUM-based change detection for Wheel_P_bad.

(c) MOSFET + wiring resistance proxy R_{mosfet_hot} with CUSUM-based change detection for Wheel_P_bad.

(d) 95th-percentile voltage sag $sag_{95\%}$ with CUSUM-based change detection for Wheel_P_bad.

Fig. A3: CUSUM charts for the stylized synthetic Wheel P trajectory (global ageing mode). The early-life logs of real Wheel P are used as reference, and late-life points where the synthetic indicators depart from this baseline are highlighted as intra-wheel regime changes. The goal is to evaluate the responsiveness of the simple CUSUM configuration under controlled knee-like degradation patterns, not to estimate real-world failure times.

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1243 Appendix B Wheel M battery swap

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1258 (a) Median equivalent pack resistance $R_{eq,median}$ vs wheel mileage for Wheel M (intra-wheel indicator).

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(b) Battery-dominated pack resistance $R_{batt,median@25^{\circ}C}$ vs wheel mileage for Wheel M.

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(c) Battery current 95th percentile i_{95p} vs wheel mileage for Wheel M.

(d) 95th-percentile voltage sag $sag_{95\%}$ vs wheel mileage for Wheel M.

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Fig. B4: Example of a wheel (Wheel M) for which the battery pack was replaced during the observation window, according to user maintenance records. The replacement appears as a step change in equivalent pack resistance, battery-dominated resistance and sag metrics, followed by a new stable regime. This illustrates how EUC_SOH highlights large intra-wheel shifts in pack-level indicators, even though it does not resolve cell-level phenomena.

Declarations	1289
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Availability of data and material	1291
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The datasets and source code used to generate the results of this paper are openly available at Zenodo https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19024289 . The repository includes the minimal analysis scripts, configuration files and example ride logs required to reproduce the figures and tables in this article. The shared logs have been made safe: GPS coordinates and personally identifying information have been removed or coarsened. Also EUCs brands/models have been replaced by generic identifiers, when relevant.	1293
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Authors' contributions	1308
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The author conceived the study, implemented the EUC SOH system and ageing simulator, carried out all analyses, and wrote and revised the manuscript.	1310
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